

THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF ALUMINIUM OXIDE SOLS

BY A. K. M. TRIVEDI AND K. M. BUCH

Concentrated aluminium oxide sol has been prepared by peptising freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide with dilute hydrochloric acid, purified by hot dialysis, and its various constituents determined. The conductivity of the sol, diluted with water, has been measured. It is concluded that bulk of the stabilising electrolyte adheres to the micelles and the sol shows the behaviour of a typical colloidal electrolyte.

According to Pauli (*Kolloid Z.*, 1921, 29, 281), colloidal aluminium oxide contains particles of the composition $[mAl(OH)_3, nAlOCl, AlO^+Cl^-]$. Thomas (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 27) also was of the view that the dispersed phase in the case of such sols consisted of oxolated aluminium oxychloride of the Werner type. On the other hand, no oxychloride of aluminium has been established with certainty (Weiser, "Colloid Chemistry", 2nd ed., 1949, p. 216). The particles of such sols may consist of $x(\gamma-Al_2O_3 \cdot H_2O) \cdot yHCl \cdot zH_2O$ with Al^{3+} and H^+ as stabilising ions and Cl^- as counter ions or gegenions*.

The nature of the stabilising electrolyte in the case of aluminium oxide sol may be investigated by electrical conductivity measurements. The conductivity of aluminium oxide sols has been determined by a number of workers (Lottermoser, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 391; Pauli and Schmidt, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 139, 199; Dhar and Chakravarti, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1927, 17, 168; Mukherjee *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1953, 83, 36; 1953, 85, 72; this *Journal*, 1953, 10, 405). In most cases, however, dilute sols were employed. In the present investigation the conductivity of concentrated aluminium oxide sols has been determined and a systematic investigation of the relation between conductivity and dilution has been carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several methods have been employed by different investigators for the preparation of aluminium oxide sols (Gay Lussac, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1810, 74, 193; Graham, *Phil. Mag.*, 1862, iv 23, 290; Schneider, *Annalen*, 1890, 287, 359; Davis, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 86, 949; Kohlshutter, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1923, 29, 253; Dhar and Mitra, this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 315; Pauli, *loc. cit.*). In the present investigation, concentrated aluminium oxide sols were prepared by the addition of ammonium hydroxide to aluminium chloride solution and then peptising aluminium hydroxide, thus formed, by dilute hydrochloric acid, and subsequently subjecting the sol to continuous hot dialysis (Neidle and Barab, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1962; 1917, 39, 71). Purified sols were carefully evaporated on the water-bath at 60-70°. It was found that the partly dialysed sol could be concentrated up to 80 g. per litre. It was remarkable that both highly purified and impure sols had a great tendency to set to a gel condition.

*Previously the term 'gegenion' was wrongly used by us for 'stabilising ion' (e. g. Trivedi and Divatia, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 131).

Aluminium oxide content of the sol was determined by evaporating the sol to dryness first in the oven at 110-20° and subsequently heating to a constant weight over a burner. Anhydrous aluminium chloride, which is volatile under this condition (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Vol. V, 1946, p. 316), escapes, leaving only aluminium oxide. Chloride content of the sol was determined as follows: To an aliquot portion of the sol excess of the sodium sulphate was added. The coagulum was digested on a sand-bath and then filtered and washed till free of chloride. An excess of calcium carbonate was added to neutralise the acid, if any, and the solution was titrated against standard silver nitrate using potassium chromate as indicator (Cumming and Kay, "A Text-Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., 1939, p. 164).

Two sols were employed for conductivity determination. Their compositions are shown below.

TABLE I

Sol.	Al ₂ O ₃ (g./litre).	AlCl ₃ (g./litre).
A	37.56	0.621
B	36.92	0.665

Water (sp. condy. = 2×10^{-8} mho) was used for dilution. As the sols were highly viscous, great care was taken for preparing different dilutions. The dilutions were further checked by analysis. The conductivity of the sols, prepared as above, was measured at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ in two series. In one of them, starting with the most concentrated sol, the conductivity of the diluted sols was successively determined. In the second series, the order was reversed. For each dilution, several readings were taken. The electrical conductivity (in mho) of the sol was measured as before (Trivedi *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 35A, 53°). Table II records the mean values of the resistances at different dilutions.

TABLE II

Sol. conc.	Resistance (ohms).	Series A.				Sol. conc.	Resistance (ohms).	Series B.			
		Sp. condnc. of micelles $\times 10^4$.	Eq. condnc. of micelles. (a)	Eq condnc. of free AlCl ₃ . (b)	Ratio a/b.			Sp. condnc. of micelles $\times 10^4$.	Eq. condnc. of micelles. (a)	Eq. condnc. of free AlCl ₃ . (b)	Ratio a/b.
37.56	330.6	6.645	47.5	143	0.33	36.92	310.4	7.076	47.1	142	0.33
34.14	371.5	5.913	45.5	145	0.32	30.75	385.4	5.699	45.6	145	0.31
28.88	440.3	4.989	46.6	147	0.31	28.39	421.4	5.214	45.2	146	0.30
26.81	475.5	4.19	46.6	148	0.31	26.35	451.1	4.871	45.4	147	0.31
25.01	515.5	4.262	45.8	149	0.30	22.15	507.2	4.332	49.1	150	0.32
18.78	659.7	3.330	47.5	151	0.30	18.45	601.1	3.655	48.7	153	0.31
9.390	1009	2.183	62.3	166	0.37	14.76	676.2	3.249	54.1	156	0.34
3.765	2408	0.912	65.1	180	0.36	3.692	2186.6	1.005	66.7	179	0.37

DISCUSSION

The aluminium oxide sol may contain aluminium oxide, aluminium chloride and HCl; the latter two may be both in the free as well as in the combined state. On testing, free H^+ and Al^{3+} were found to be absent, Al^{3+} ion being tested with 8-hydroxyquinoline (Berg., *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 369). Hence, it may be concluded that aluminium chloride is the only stabilising electrolyte under the experimental conditions and most of it is present in the combined state. Assuming that conductivity of the sol is due to micelles only, the equivalent conductivity of the micelles can be found out. The molecular conductivity of aluminium chloride in the free state has been obtained from the data of Jones (Carnegie Institution of Washington, Publication No. 170, 1912) and Bjerrum (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 59, 336). Table II shows the equivalent conductivity of the micelles, of free aluminium chloride ($\frac{1}{3}$ molecular conductivity) and the ratio of the two.

In all cases, it is obvious that the eq. conductivity of the micelles is much smaller than that of free aluminium chloride, the actual ratio being about 0.3 to 0.4. Hence, the bulk of the stabilising electrolyte adheres to the micelles, the behaviour being similar to that of sulphur sol (Bolam and Trivedi, *Trans Faraday Soc.*, 1943, 39, 247), iron oxide sol (Trivedi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and chromium oxide sol (Trivedi, Bhatt and Divatia, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 116). In the case of aluminium oxide sol, again, the degree of dissociation of the stabilising electrolyte appears to be rather high as in the case of chromium oxide sol. The higher value may be due to the fact that the sol may

FIG. 1

contain free electrolyte, not allowed for in the calculations. At any rate, the bulk of the stabilising electrolyte adheres to the micelles. If we compare the variation of the conductivity of the micelles, on dilution, with the variation of the conductivity of free aluminium chloride on similar dilution, it is found that unlike the free electrolyte, the eq. conductivity of the micelles first decreases and then increases on further dilution. This is shown graphically in the case of sol B. The behaviour of aluminium oxide sol is in harmony with that shown by iron oxide and chromium oxide sols (*loc. cit.*).

Hence, like soap solutions, such systems may be classified amongst colloidal electrolytes (McBain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1636).

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